

Characterization of Endophytic Bacterial Strains Isolated from Rice Grain Discoloration

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to isolate bacterial species obtained from different rice varieties: Kainat, Basmati-385, Super basmati, Basmati 86, KSK-133, Basmati-198, Basmati-2000x1053-2-2, Kasur, Stg 567989 and Basmati-2000x33797-1 collected from all agro ecological zones of Pakistan. When plated infected grain samples gave various bacterial colonies on Luria Bertani (L.B) agar medium. The isolates were identified on the basis of various morphological and biochemical features. Out of 22 isolates, five showed rod cell shape in microscope. Sixteen biochemical tests were conducted to characterize 22 isolates of bacteria. Gram stain demonstrated that three isolates were gram positive and rod shaped. All other isolates were gram negative. The presence of bacteria was also estimated in ten different varieties of rice. The highest presence of bacteria was observed in KSK-133, Kainat and Stg 567989. *Burkholderia* species and *Enterobacter* species have high frequency almost in all tested rice varieties. The overall objective of this study was to screen, classify and associate the bacterial species present on the basis of various morphological characteristics isolated from diverse rice

genotype. The results demonstrated that collected and investigated rice varieties have a diverse range of bacterial species, some of which are considered as severe pathogens for plants.

Key Words: Rice grains, bacteria, isolation, identification, characterization

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is one of the most important cereal grains and a staple food of more than 50% of the world's population. Crop productivity is based on numerous variables including weather, soil type, moisture, and nutrients (Luo *et al.*, 1998). In Pakistan, grain yield/unit area of rice is very low as compared to other developed countries of the world and this low production is attributed to several biotic and abiotic factors. Among the biotic factors, disease is the most important factor, which results in yield losses every year. Diseases causes' extensive damage to rice and severity of infection varies with different species and varieties (Asghar *et al.*, 2007). Rice is attacked by fungi, bacteria, viruses, mycoplasma like organisms and nematodes causing 76 diseases (Hajano *et al.*, 2012). Discoloration, blights, rots, blotch are a complex disease symptoms of rice due to infection by certain microorganisms on the glumes, kernels, or both (Arshad *et al.*, 2009). The goal of the present work was to isolate, purify and identify bacteria from different varieties of rice and their frequency distribution in all varieties. Rice grain discoloration is becoming a series threat to the Pakistan rice varieties and in Asia as a whole and is more severe with passage of time (Arshad *et al.*, 2009; Phat *et al.*, 2005). Discoloration decreases the yield potential of rice crop along with other diseases, and account for the yield losses up to 6% (Savary *et al.*, 2000). Rice grain discoloration affects the qualitative and quantitative traits (Sumangala *et al.*, 2009; Tariq *et al.*, 2012) and is ultimately responsible for

yield reduction and other desirable traits. Rice yield is also affected by many biotic factors i.e. infected brown spot grain disease, insects and other prevalent diseases (Hajano *et al.*, 2012; Sumangala *et al.*, 2009; Jabeen *et al.*, 2012). Losses due to brown spot infected grains have been recorded in the range of 16% to 43% (Datnoff *et al.*, 1997). These diseases affect the grain quality, break of rice during milling, weight loss, exports, post harvest losses, crop yield and ultimately badly affect the economy of Pakistan (Ghazanfar *et al.*, 2013). Rice diseases can be managed by the use of pesticides, growth of resistant varieties, change in agronomic practices and use of various new biotechnological methods (Ribot *et al.*, 2008). However, the use of resistant varieties is the most economical and environmental friendly method for the management of diseases but the use of resistance varieties fails due to appearance of new/more virulent strains of the pathogen (Ghazanfar *et al.*, 2009). The objectives of this study were to (1) Isolation of endophytic bacterial strains from rice having grain discoloration symptoms. (2) Categorization of bacterial species with respect to their different morphological traits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Rice Varieties

The frequency of bacterial population was estimated in diseased rice grains. Different varieties of diseased rice grains were collected from Kala Shah Kaku (KSK), Lahore, Pakistan and USA (USDA, Arkansas) as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: List of different Rice varieties with their source

Sr. No	Name of Rice Varieties	Accession No.	Source	Collection site
01	Kainat	NA	Subcontinent	Gujranwala
02	Basmati-385	Approved Variety	KSK, Pakistan	Sheikhupura
03	Super basmati	Approved Variety	KSK, Pakistan	Gujranwala
04	Basmati- 386	Approved Variety	KSK, Pakistan	Gujranwala, Sialkot
05	KSK-133	Approved Variety	KSK, Pakistan	Hafizabad, Sheikhupura
06	Basmati-198	Approved Variety	KSK, Pakistan	Lahore
07	Basmati-2000 x 1053-2-2	F ₄	KSK, Pakistan	PU, IAGS
08	Kasur	NA	Punjab, Pakistan	Hafizabad
09	Stg 567989	GSOR 311705	USA, Arkansas	PU, IAGS
10	Basmati-2000 x 33797-1	F ₄	KSK, Pakistan	PU, IAGS

Media Preparation

Luria Bertani agar (LBA) medium (Difco) was used for bacterial isolation (Ali and Naseem, 2012; 2011). LBA medium (High media) was prepared by dissolving Trypton: 10.0 g; NaCl: 5.0 g; Yeast extract: 5.0 g and Agar: 15.0 g in distilled water. Before adding agar pH was adjusted to 7.4. Media was sterilized by autoclaving at 15 lb. pressure for 15 minutes and plates were prepared.

Surface sterilization of Diseased Rice Grains

Rice grains with symptoms of disease were washed in running tap water and classified by surface appearance in order to exclude samples that showed superficial damage. Surface sterilization was done by stepwise washing in 70% ethanol for 5 min, sodium hypochlorite solution for 5 min, and 70% ethanol for 30 second, followed by three rinses in sterile distilled water (Araujo *et al.*, 2002).

Isolation of bacterial strains

The surface sterilized diseased rice grains were cut into pieces 2 to 3 mm long, which were placed on LBA medium (g/L) plates. Incubation was carried out at 37°C for 24 hours to allow growth of endophytic bacteria from the cut pieces. In another experiment, fragments of diseased rice grains were homogenized in 5 ml of sterile saline solution with a blender and serial dilutions (1ml of 10⁵) were spread with sterilized spreader onto LBA medium (Ali and Naseem, 2011). The plates were placed in an incubator at 37°C for 24 hours. Streaking of isolates was done to obtain individual colonies on agar plates (Beishir, 1991). Pure bacterial cultures were stored in 20% sterile glycerol at -20 °C until further analysis.

Identification of bacterial strains

Identification of bacterial species was done by recording phenotypic characteristics, e.g., colony morphology, colony color, cell shape, motility and growth rate. The purified colonies were subjected to gram staining and characterized using biochemical tests and consulting the pertinent literature (Holt *et al.*, 2000; Koneman *et al.*, 1997; Benson, 1996). Bacteria were

identified by providing the results of all above mentioned biochemical tests to Microgen Identification System software. The relative abundance/frequency (%) of each bacterial isolated by dilution plating was also calculated as: (Number of colonies of a bacterial species/ total number of bacterial colonies) \times 100 (Mukhtar *et al.*, 2012).

RESULTS

Bacterial species isolated on the L.B agar medium from different rice varieties collected from Kala Shah Kaku (KSK), Lahore, Pakistan and USA (USDA, Arkansas) were used in this study. All isolates were purified by serial dilution with sterile distilled water and plating on LBA medium. The bacterial colonies on these plates were examined for their morphological characteristics. Single colonies, with different cultural characteristics, from each culture plate were touched with a flamed bacteriological loop and streaked on LBA medium, incubated at 37°C for 24 hr, and then stored in micro-centrifuge tubes at -20°C in 20% glycerol. Bacterial strains were removed from the freezer as needed for identification and plated on LBA medium (Table 2-4). Frequency distribution of bacterial species as shown in Table 4 and Figure 1 and 2 was different within varieties and location. The frequency of bacteria from KSK-133, Basmati-385, Kainat and Stg 567989 was higher than that of Basmati-86, Basmati-198 and Kasur. It was found that *B. pseudomallai*, *B. glumae*, *E. asburiae* and *A. facilis* have high frequency almost in all tested varieties (Figure 1 and 2).

Table 2: An Outline of the Morphological Characters of Bacterial species Isolated from Rice

Grains (+): positive reaction; (-): Negative reaction.

Strain No.	Morphological characters									
	Colony color	Colony texture	Reverse color	Odour	Cell Shape	Gram Stain	Capsule Stain	Motility test	Growth on 5% NaCl	Growth on 5% Glucose
01	Off white	Slimy	Yellow	+	Cocci	-	-	-	-	+
02	Off white	Slimy	Yellow	+	Cocci	-	-	-	+	+
03	Off white	Slimy	Yellow	+	Cocci	-	-	-	-	+
04	White	Slimy	White	-	Cocci	-	-	+	+	+
05	White	Slimy	White	-	Cocci	-	-	-	+	+
06	White	Slimy	White	-	Cocci	-	-	-	+	+
07	White	Rough slimy	White	-	Cocci	-	-	+	-	+
08	White	Rough slimy	White	-	Cocci	-	-	+	+	+
09	Dusty white	Dry crust	White	+	Rods	+	-	+	+	+
10	Dusty white	Dry crust	White	+	Rods	+	-	-	-	-
11	Dusty white	Dry crust	White	+	Rods	+	-	+	+	-
12	Off	Slimy	Light	-	Rods	-	-	-	+	-

	white		yellow							
13	Off white	Slimy	Light yellow	-	Rods	-	-	-	+	-
14	Off white	Slimy	White	-	Cocci	-	-	+	-	-
15	Bright yellow	Slimy	Yellow	-	Cocci	-	-	+	+	+
16	Bright yellow	Slimy	Yellow	-	Cocci	-	-	-	+	+
17	Bright yellow	Slimy	Yellow	-	Cocci	-	-	+	+	+-
18	Dirt white	Slimy	White	-	Cocci	-	-	-	-	+
19	Dirty white	Slimy	White	-	Cocci	-	-	+	+	-
20	White	Slimy	White	-	Cocci	-	-	-	+	+
21	White	Slimy	White	-	Cocci	-	-	+	+	-
22	White	Slimy	White	-	Cocci	-	-	+	+	-

Table 3: An Outline of the Biochemical Tests of Bacterial species Isolated from Rice Grains (+):

positive reaction; (-): Negative reaction.

Strain	Biochemical Tests	Identified Bacterial
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No	Lysine Test	Glucose Test	Raffinose Test	Arabinose Test	Nitrate Reductase	Oxidase Test	Urease Test	Methyl Red Test	Citrate Utilization	Hydrogen Sulfide	Catalase Test	Indole Test	Rhamnose Test	Mannitol Test	Xylose Test	Sorbitol Test	Species
01	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	<i>Enterobacter asburiae</i>
02	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Enterobacter</i> sp.
03	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	<i>E. cloacae</i>
04	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	<i>Acidovorax</i> sp.
05	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>A. temperans</i>
06	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	<i>A. facilis</i>
07	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Citrobacter</i> sp.
08	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>C diversus</i>
09	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	<i>Kurthia</i> sp.
10	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	-	<i>K. sibirica</i>
11	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	<i>K. zopfii</i>
12	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	<i>Acinetobacter</i> sp.
13	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>A. junii</i>
14	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	<i>Kluyvera</i> sp.
15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	<i>Xanthobacter</i> sp.
16	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	<i>X. agilis</i>
17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>X. flavus</i>
18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>Aureobacterium</i> sp.
19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>A. liquefaciens</i>

20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>Burkholderia</i> sp.
21	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>B. glumae</i>
22	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	<i>B. pseudomallei</i>

Table 4: Number of colonies of bacterial species from different varieties of Rice grains

S. No.	Diseased Rice Grains sample Collection	Rice Varieties	Total No. of Bacteria	Bacterial species	No. of colonies	Culture media (g/L)
1	Gujranwala, KSK, Pakistan	Kainat	10	<i>Acidovorax</i> sp.	03	Luria Bertani Agar(NA)
				<i>Enterobacter</i> sp.	02	=
				<i>Acidovorax temperans</i>	02	=
				<i>Kurthia zopfii</i>	03	=
2	Sheikhupura, KSK, Pakistan	Basmati-385	08	<i>Burkholderia</i> sp.	03	=
				<i>Acidovorax temperans</i>	02	=
				<i>Enterobacter asburiae</i>	02	=
				<i>Aureobacterium</i> sp.	01	=
3	Gujranwala, KSK, Pakistan	Super basmati	07	<i>Burkholderia pseudomallei</i>	02	=
				<i>Acidovorax facilis</i>	03	=
				<i>Citrobacter</i> sp.	01	=
				<i>Aureobacterium liquefaciens</i>	01	=
4	Gujranwala,	Basmati 86	05	<i>Acinetobacter junii</i>	02	=
				<i>Burkholderia glumae</i>	02	=

	Sialkot KSK, Pakistan			<i>Aureobacterium</i> sp.	01	=
5	Hafizabad, Sheikhupura, KSK, Pakistan	KSK-133	11	<i>Kurthia sibirica</i>	04	=
				<i>Acidovorax facilis</i>	03	=
				<i>Xanthobacter agilis</i>	02	=
				<i>Burkholderia glumae</i>	02	=
6	Lahore, Pakistan	Basmati-198	05	<i>Kluyvera</i> sp.	01	=
				<i>Enterobacter asburiae</i>	02	=
				<i>Aureobacterium liquefaciens</i>	01	=
				<i>Burkholderia glumae</i>	01	=
7	IAGS, P.U, Lahore	Basmati- 2000x1053-2-2	07	<i>Burkholderia pseudomallei</i>	02	=
				<i>Citrobacter diversus</i>	02	=
				<i>Enterobacter</i> sp.	03	=
8	Hafizabad, Sheikhupura, KSK, Pakistan	Kasur	05	<i>Acidovorax facilis</i>	01	=
				<i>Acinetobacter junii</i>	01	=
				<i>Burkholderia glumae</i>	01	=
				<i>Xanthobacter flavus</i>	02	=
9	IAGS, P.U, Lahore	Stg 567989	09	<i>Burkholderia glumae</i>	01	=
				<i>Xanthobacter agilis</i>	04	=
				<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	02	=
				<i>Kurthia</i> sp.	02	=
10	IAGS, P.U,	Basmati-	07	<i>Acinetobacter</i> sp.	01	=

Lahore	2000x33797-1	<i>Enterobacter asburiae</i>	03	=
		<i>Xanthobacter sp.</i>	02	=
		<i>Burkholderia glumae</i>	01	=
		Total	77	

Figure 1: Percentage of Bacterial spp. isolated from each Rice varieties

Figure 2: Occurrence of Bacterial spp. in each Rice samples

DISCUSSION

All isolated bacterial species were identified by recording macroscopic, macroscopic and biochemical characters and classified using Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology (9th Edition). Colony morphology gave an indication of variation among bacterial strains. Purification of bacterial species was done due to uniqueness or differences with other in colony morphology (Ali *et al.*, 2013).

The identified bacterial species that was isolated from rice grains included: *Enterobacter* sp., *E. asburiae*, *E. cloacae*, *Acidovorax* sp., *A. temperans*, *A. facilis*, *Citrobacter* sp., *C. diversus*, *Kurthia* sp., *K. sibirica*, *K. zopfii*, *Acinetobacter* sp., *A. junii*, *Kluyvera* sp., *Xanthobacter* sp., *X. agilis*, *X. flavus*, *Aureobacterium* sp., *A. liquefaciens*, *Burkholderia* sp., *B. glumae* and *B. pseudomallei*. Of the 22 identified bacterial species three were gram positive and nineteen gram negative. The cell shapes of five bacterial species were bacilli (rod) and the other were cocci. Interestingly, Gram positive and Gram negative isolates were equally distributed between all rice varieties. An earlier study reported a predominance of Gram negative bacteria in the tissues of rice grains (Ashfaq *et al.*, 2013). However, Akhtar *et al.* (2013) reported an equal presence of Gram negative and Gram positive bacteria in microfauna of Lahore soil. Pathogens associated with discolored rice grain disease have been reported before (Khan *et al.*, 2000; Javed *et al.*, 2002). Rice yield reduction is caused by many rice diseases and worldwide it is estimated to be about 14-18% (Mew *et al.*, 2004; Mew and Gonzales, 2002). Some areas have heavy yield losses ranging from 50 to 90% (Agrios, 2005). In Tamil Nadu India yield losses up to 39% were reported (Shanmugam *et al.*, 2006). Rice grain discoloration is also a major limiting factor in rice

yield (Rajpan *et al.*, 2001). Rice molecular markers also play a very important role for screening, selection and identifying the new resistant rice lines against diseases and other biotic and abiotic stresses (Choudhary *et al.*, 2013; Pinta *et al.*, 2013).

CONCLUSION

The diversity and characterization of different bacterial species isolated from diverse rice germplasm lines were classified. The study may be utilized for the screening of various rice germplasm lines on the basis of various isolated bacterial species and classification of the genotypes with respect to their various kinds of pathogen. This study may also equally helpful for the scientist and farmers community for the classification (on the basis of resistant, tolerant and susceptibility of rice genotypes against various pathogens and also provides the information for further investigation in to new insight in scientific field.

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